

20.06.2022

Dear Editor,

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I am a faculty member at Trakya University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Radiation Oncology. Among the patients I personally follow are breast cancer patients. The clinical experiences I gained from my patients I followed for years encouraged me to do my study, which I have presented in the appendix. We tried to reflect our clinical experience retrospectively. We trust our data first, as our file information is regularly and closely monitored. It is very valuable for us to present your valuable scientists' opinions. Thanks to the guidance and encouragement of **Ms. Tina Hong**, I would like you to evaluate my article. I think that retrospective data is important because it reflects a certain experience such as old age. The publication you see is the work of years.

“BREAST CANCER SUBTYPES AND PROGNOSIS: ANSWERS TO SUBGROUP CLASSIFICATION QUESTIONS, IDENTIFYING THE WORST SUBGROUP IN OUR SINGLE-CENTER SERIES”

I present our study titled to your attention and submit it to your information to be evaluated for publication in your journal.

Best regards

Assoc.Prof. Dr. Rusen Cosar

